

Webis at Sim4IA 2025

Prediction of Next User Queries as a Sequence-To-Sequence Problem

Marcel Gohsen

Bauhaus-Universität
Weimar

Matthias Hagen

Benno Stein

[webis.de]

Next Query Prediction

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Modeling next query prediction as a sequence-to-sequence problem:

- **Input:** $Q = (q_1, \dots, q_n)$
Sequence of queries from a search session.
- **Output:** $\hat{Q} = (q_{n+1}, \dots, q_{n+\lambda})$
Sequence of plausible future queries.

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Possible sequence encoding:

$\langle | \text{bos} | \rangle q_1 \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle q_2 \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle \dots \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle q_n \langle | \text{eos} | \rangle$

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Can language models learn this sequence effectively?

Training Procedure

0. Start with pretrained language model
GPT-2 base or medium.
1. Query pretraining
Learning how to complete single queries.
2. Session fine-tuning
Learning how to complete a search session and meaning of `<|sep|>`
3. Domain-specific fine-tuning
Learning how to complete Sim4IA-specific search sessions

Training Data

(1. query pretraining)

Dataset	All		Filtered	
	Queries	Sessions	Queries	Sessions
Archive Query Log	51,298,196	–	13,390,050	–
<i>dblp.org</i>	5,762,062	–	3,059,788	–
<i>google.com</i>	20,023,180	–	5,227,488	–
<i>scholar.google.com</i>	25,512,954	–	5,102,774	–
AOL Query Log	16,946,938	657,426	446,608	63,119
Sim4IA Training Set	176	45	176	45

Reimer et al., 2023. The Archive Query Log: Mining Millions of Search Result Pages of Hundreds of Search Engines from 25 Years of Web Archives.

AOL Query Log: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/dineshydv/aol-user-session-collection-500k>

Training Data

(2. session fine-tuning)

Dataset	All		Filtered	
	Queries	Sessions	Queries	Sessions
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(3. domain-specific fine-tuning)

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Filter Heuristics

Exclude queries that...

- ❑ contain only one term,
'Data'
- ❑ contain more than 10 query terms,
'A reparameterization and monitoring platform for energy efficient GPS trackers in behavioural analysis of wildlife.'
- ❑ are not in English language,
'SGML - XML - HTML: Gemeinsamkeiten und Unterschiede.'
- ❑ or contain more than two full stops.
'Ellen Mazur Thomson. Aesthetic Tracts: Innovation in Late-Nineteenth Century Book Design. New Castle, Del.: Oak Knoll Press, 2015. 208p. Cloth, \$55.00 (ISBN 9781584563365).'

Inference

Input: $\langle | \text{bos} | \rangle q_1 \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle q_2 \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle \dots \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle q_n \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle$

Output: $q_{n+1} \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle q_{n+2} \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle \dots \langle | \text{sep} | \rangle q_{n+\lambda} \langle | \text{eos} | \rangle$

Decoding:

- ❑ Diverse Beam Search
- ❑ 10 beams for top-10 queries
- ❑ Moderate diversity penalty of 1.5

Example Outputs

Sometimes it works...

q_1 *new york*

q_2 *new york accomodation*

q_3 *new york attractions*

q_4 *the new york zoo*

q_1 *passivation*

q_2 *acid passivation*

q_3 *stainless acid passivation*

q_4 *sodium chloride passivation*

q_5 *sodium chloride*

Example Outputs

Sometimes it works...

q_1 *new york*
 q_2 *new york accomodation*
 q_3 *new york attractions*

 q_4 *the new york zoo*

q_1 *passivation*
 q_2 *acid passivation*
 q_3 *stainless acid passivation*

 q_4 *sodium chloride passivation*
 q_5 *sodium chloride*

... sometimes it doesn't.

q_1 *new york*
 q_2 *new york accomodation*
 q_3 *new york attractions*

 q_4 *toyota*
 q_5 *toyota cars*
 q_6 *toyota cars for sale*

q_1 *passivation*
 q_2 *acid passivation*
 q_3 *stainless acid passivation*

 q_4 *stainless acid passivation recipe*
 q_5 *stainless acid passivation recipe for baking*

Submitted Runs

- ❑ `webis-qpt2`
GPT-2 base + query pretraining + session fine-tuning + domain-specific fine-tuning
- ❑ `webis-qpt2-medium`
GPT-2 medium + query pretraining + session fine-tuning + domain-specific fine-tuning
- ❑ `webis-gpt2`
GPT-2 base + session fine-tuning + domain-specific fine-tuning
- ❑ `webis-expert-manual1`
IR researcher extracting keyphrases from search results
- ❑ `webis-expert-manual2`
IR researcher who exploits Google's query suggestions

Submitted Runs

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Thank you!